

Recommended citation: Järvinen, H., Niemelä, P., & Ulla-Talvikki, V. (2019). Combining flipped ideas and online learning. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 566-577). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656483.

Combining Flipped Ideas and Online Learning

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ABSTRACT

Flipped classroom and flipped learning are quickly expanding in Finnish university pedagogy. In particular, videos and other distance learning options are preferred by such students who are already working while finalizing their studies.

This flipped learning experiment was executed in five implementations of two courses (2016–2018). Flipped learning was carried out as a partial application: first, students read the topics in advance; second, they were supposed to make questions or otherwise affect on the contents of the lectures. Questions were implemented as weekly tasks to be completed in the learning management systems. The questions comprised both post- and pre-tasks. The post-task scanned the past lecture and pre-test one about the topics of the upcoming lecture. In addition, there was a comment section, where the students could leave questions about the topics they would like to be discussed in more detail in an upcoming lecture.

In results, we will discuss the correlation between the weekly activity, assignment and exam points and examine the functionality of the system.

Conference Key areas: Open and Online Teaching and Learning, Integrated learning environments for the digital native learners

Keywords: Flipped classroom, online course

1 INTRODUCTION

Digitalisation manifests itself in the realm of education, where the current era of the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) has led to accelerated automation and digitalisation of services [1]. As a symptom of digitalisation, current university students in Finland implicitly assume downloadable learning materials; traditional printed matter starts to be scarce. Learning management systems (LMSs) progress from simple pdf

repositories and course point databases into ones promoting social interactions and collaborative problem solving among participants. In addition to formal learning resources, the students exploit extensively online materials such as videos, games, virtual worlds, and free online MOOCs, which further fosters informal learning practises and blending them with formal education [2].

MOOCs can be divided into extension MOOC (xMOOC) and connectivist MOOC (cMOOC) [3, 4]. In xMOOC, multiple functions, such as assessment, can be highly automated [5], so the contact with a teacher gets thinner, and contacts with peers cease to exist, whereas in the development of cMOOC, a trend of providing opportunities for more social interaction is emphasized, like the evolution of more socially geared LMSs. cMOOC facilitates fellowship activities such as group work and peer review. These social elements are found to be important in getting some students more committed, activating them and forming communities [6, 7].

Senior university students prefer distant and remote learning opportunities: MOOC-like courses are appreciated. At the same time in education, the ideas of the flipped classroom and flipped learning are trending with the promise of improved and intensified learning. However, combining the MOOC—or even parts of it—with flipped learning is not straightforward. This paper describes the steps towards flipped learning in selected courses, and examines the effect on learning outcomes. The main questions we address in this paper are:

1. What are the means to increase activity in the flipped learning when the interactive component of the lectures is missing?
2. Can this be implemented with a lower number of faculty hours?
3. Which are the first observations of the effects of the flipped learning practices on learning outcomes?

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 contains a review of flipped learning, Section 3 describes the research context, Section 4 introduces the results, and the last section discusses the results and the future ideas to improve the approach.

2 ABOUT FLIPPED LEARNING

Some categorisation factors of MOOC, such as autonomy and social interaction, comply with the self-determination theory (SDT) of Deci and Ryan [8–10]. However, the third ingredient of SDT, the felt competence, is not that apparent. Supposedly, competence increases instinctively by deepening the substance knowledge. A good learning solution follows SDT principles and provides options for autonomy.

SDT theory is fulfilled in flipped learning that has attracted teachers seeking a more studentcentered way of learning after the hegemony of traditional learning culture. First, in the model of flipped teaching, students familiarise themselves with materials, such as text, videos and podcasts, and complete pre-tasks before arriving at a contact lesson or lecture. On the contrary to the past, lectures are not based on teachers' monologues, but instead on collaborative tasks such as group work targeting information retrieval and deepening skills [11].

Toivola and Silfverberg [12] unveil the difference between flipped learning and flipped classroom that can be considered conceptually inconsequential, but still separable in the continuum of teacher- to learner-centered didactic approaches, see Figure 1.

In the flipped classroom, a teacher still keeps the control to decide what will happen in the classroom and allocates the time for learning. In the flipped learning, in contrast, a teacher dares to give up direct control and trusts students' ability and desire to learn, thus transferring

Figure 1: The dimensional view of the didactic approaches in the continuum from directed teaching towards learner-centred learning according to Toivola and Silfverberg [12].

the responsibility of the progress more to the student.

However, the strength of the flipped learning, i.e., the increased autonomy and responsibility of students may turn to be the biggest problem for adapting the flipped learning approach. Instead of the anticipated empowerment in regard to their own learning, some students may be left overwhelmed and clueless of how to proceed and study. Therefore, the amount of required autonomy should thus gradually increase and be at its largest at the end of the studies.

3 RESEARCH CONTEXT

The study is conducted in two courses, software testing and software architectures. Both courses belong to master level studies. Two consecutive implementations (years 2017 and 2018) of software testing are analysed, the first one without any online component and the second one with online exercises designed to support flipped ideas. For the software architecture course, three implementations (years 2016, 2017 and 2018) are studied. The first implementation was a traditional one with regular exercises, assignments and lectures. The second one had online exercises but the tasks were traditional post-lecture type only. On the third implementation, the weekly online exercises were altered to have one task post-lecture type and pre-lecture type.

3.1 Method

Design-based research (DBR) is a method of systematizing the practical process of developing an artifact which in the field of education can be, i.e., curriculum, or a new

learning method, or as in this case, courses transferred to the direction of flipped learning [13–15]. A nominal feature of the design-based research is the development in cycles. Each design cycle comprises the phases of design, development, enactment, and analysis, which inserts new requirements into the redesign of the course [16, 17]. The cyclic development complies with subsequent course iterations; the courses are kept once a year. The lecturer remains the same, and the content alters only to a small extent between iterations, thus, the major alteration is due to the changes towards flipped ideas.

In the design phase, the learning targets of the courses are checked and harmonized with the content of other courses and the objectives of the curriculum. Development is mainly executed by the course personnel, but it includes dialogue with researchers in education. For example, the emphasis on flipped learning, and formative assessment with a peer-review rubrics may partly be backtracked to these discussions. Enactment inherently includes reflections on the functionality of new changes by the lecturer and teaching assistants. To complete the course, the students have to give feedback in the learning management system (LMS). In addition, the responsible teacher has to answer their feedback after the commenting period is out. The analysis of the course is based on the student feedback which is compared with the results of previous course iterations. The learning outcomes are compared against the course objectives.

3.2 Changes in the course environment

In the academic year 2016-2017, the university obtained the possibility to record lectures. The videos are available for the students after the lectures; however, live watching is not supported. In the software architecture course, Adobe Connect [18] had been used for some years, since the lectures were followed at another university. Adobe Connect provides a possibility also for individual students to follow the lectures live and make questions either orally or in writing. Hence, there were experiences of online lecturing with a possibility for the remote interaction, albeit they very rarely used the possibility; it was mostly used to notify problems in connection (*'I can't hear, please put the microphone on'*). After the university installed the automatic recording system, all courses were recorded by default. However, the lecturers have a possibility to cancel recording but they seldom do that, since students are keen to have the records. The records can be followed only afterwards and the system is not interactive. Consequently, this setup differs remarkably from the online lecturing conventions of standard MOOCs.

For both courses, there was a new responsible teacher since the earlier lecturers left the university. Unfortunately, new faculty members could not be hired to replace them. This meant that the courses had to be implemented with a smaller team than before.

3.3 Towards flipped ideas

The flipped classroom ideas had been used successfully in other courses of the university and when the lecturer of the courses changed, he wanted to move in that direction. Combining the flipped classroom with one-way recorded lectures is impossible as such. However, some ideas of the flipped classroom can be brought into this environment. These are

- reading the material in advance and

- making notes or questions that have an effect on the contents of the lectures.

These were implemented by introducing weekly exercises on an online environment (later referred to as flipped online exercises). Each week (except for those having a guest lecture) there were two or three tasks:

- one about the topics of the previous lecture (in the architecture course only)
- one about the topics of the upcoming lecture
- writing a comment where the student could ask something to be emphasised or explained better on the forthcoming lecture.

The first two tasks provided activity points for students, weight being on the upcoming topics.

3.4 Grading of the courses

The target was to reduce the role of the final examination as the major foundation for grading. Originally, the assignments had only a minor effect on the final grade rewarded by a few extra points in the examination. In the renewed system, the examination and the assignments were given the same relative weight: they affected the final grade equally (3/7 each). Thus, to complete the course, a student has to pass both the examination and the assignments.

Other smaller, online exercises were not compulsory but to encourage students to accomplish them, they were granted the weight of 1/7 in grading. In the testing course, the points of the online exercises and the fortnightly exercises (assignments) were combined.

3.5 Course evolution

The differences between the implementations of the testing course are collected into Table 1. Both implementations had lectures, guest lectures and fortnightly exercises targeted on practical skills like using the testing tools and environments. The assignment was two-phase teamwork done in pairs.

Table 1: Main changes between implementations of the testing course

	2017	2018
Lectures	trad., no recordings, 42h	recorded, 42h
Exercises	trad. fortnightly	fortnightly + weekly online post- and pre-tasks
Assignment	two-phase	two-phase
Examination	4 questions	3 questions

Three versions of the software architecture course were studied. All versions comprised an assignment, exercises, guest lectures and lectures. The assignments were made in groups of 4–5 students. Due to the transfer towards flipping, the implementations of all these parts have changes during the three-year research period. These changes are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Main changes between implementations of the architecture course

	2016	2017	2018
Lectures	live, 42h	live and recorded, 28h	recorded, 28h
Exercises	trad. classroom	online, post-tasks	online, post- and pre-tasks
Assignment	several phases, peer	two-phase, peer	two-phase, peer
Examination	4 questions	4 questions	3 questions
Language	Finnish	English	English

Figure 2 illustrates how the implementations have evolved during 2016–2018. Notably, other aspects have influenced the placement in the timeline in addition to the transfer towards flipped learning.

4 RESULTS

Since the grading of courses included online exercises, assignment and examination, all the components of grading naturally have a positive correlation with the final grade. The most interesting correlations in this study are the correlations between exercises and the examination and assignment to see if the online exercises of new kind have an effect on learning. The

Figure 2: The testing and architecture courses situated in the continuum of flipped learning.

fortnightly exercises and attending the guest lectures were combined to "activity points" with the online exercises in the grading but as the effect of the online exercises was the main interest, their internal points are separated in the following.

Students not attending any of the three examinations available after the course were considered dropouts and left out of the statistics. Since most of them had not done anything else either, this actually decreased the correlations between other components of grading and the examination. If a student had attended several

examinations, only the first one would be taken into account, since the student was likely to study much more in the later iterations either to pass the examination or to improve his or her grade.

For all the correlations, the two-tailed Student's test was used to compute their significance. On the tables below, values above the diagonal are correlations, and values below the diagonal are their p-values indicating significance. The p-value flagged with one asterisk implies a statistically significant correlation ($p \leq 0.05$); in case of two asterisks, the correlation is very significant ($p \leq 0.001$).

4.1 Software testing course

In 2017 and 2018, the software testing course had a two-part assignment, fortnightly exercises, guest lectures, a debate, and an examination. The students got some activity points from attending the debate; the function of the debate is to activate students and improve their oral skills, which, however, is not in the scope of this paper.

For the first implementation of the testing course in 2017, there are data on assignments and exercises only. The correlation between assignments and examination is 0.2634. With 105 students attending, this correlation is significant ($p = 0.0066$).

For the second implementation, all the correlations are very significant as shown in Table 3. Very significant correlations between the online exercises and the assignment and the examination support the hypothesis that the online questions will help to pass the course and get better grades.

The very significant correlation between fortnightly exercises and the assignment is mostly explained by the fact that the fortnightly exercises were designed to support the assignment.

	Flipped online exercises	Fortnightly exercises	Assignment	Examination
Flipped online exercises	1	$r = 0.78$	$r = 0.52$	$r = 0.42$
Fortnightly exercises	$**p < 0.0001$	1	$r = 0.45$	$r = 0.42$
Assignment	$**p < 0.0001$	$**p < 0.0001$	1	$r = 0.50$
Examination	$**p < 0.0001$	$**p = 0.0004$	$**p < 0.0001$	1

plained by the fact that the fortnightly exercises were designed to support the assignment.

4.2 Software architecture course

Three versions of the software architecture course are studied as mentioned above, and their differences are collected into Table 2. Next, the correlations between different course components will be reviewed.

4.2.1 The first implementation in 2016

The first version was quite a traditional one. The weekly exercises were classroom exercises and the students could collect activity points by attendance.

Table 4: Correlations and their significance in the architecture course, 2016, n=71

	Classroom exercises	Assignment	Examination
Classroom exercises	1	$r=0.43$	$r=0.39$
Assignment	** $p=0.0002$	1	$r=0.18$
Examination	** $p=0.0008$	$p=0.1244$	1

As it can be seen from Table 4, classroom exercises correlate strongly with the other graded components of the course. The correlation between the assignment and the examination is not significant and actually quite low.

4.2.2 The second implementation in 2017

The architecture live lectures were streamed to another university and experiences gained on Adobe Connect were encouraging. However, adding automatic recording, and especially streaming and recording simultaneously proved to be tedious and error-prone. Furthermore, the new lecturer decreased the number of lectures by one third and changed the language of instruction into English. The debate that was used in the testing course was left out because students at the other university would not have the possibility to join the debate.

The classroom exercises were replaced with online exercises but the tasks followed the traditional style of post-lecture questions. There were two tasks each week. The assignment was replaced with a two-phase assignment where the first part was to design an architecture of the given system. On the second part, the students studied how the architectural design of other groups would stand a change in requirements and reported the results as a peer review.

In this version, the correlation between exercises and the assignment drops below the significance level. However, exercises still have a very significant correlation with the examination. It is noteworthy that the correlation between the assignment and the examination is not significant; actually, it is slightly negative.

Table 5: Correlations and their significance in the architecture course, 2017, n=105

	Online exercises	Assignment	Examination
Online exercises	1	$r=0.22$	$r=0.41$
Assignment	$p=0.0549$	1	$r=-0.06$
Examination	** $p=0.0003$	$p=0.6304$	1

4.2.3 The third implementation in 2018

The third implementation differed from the second one in one point only: the second task of online exercises was a pre-task concerning the forthcoming lecture. The students could also ask for some topics to be discussed in lectures.

Table 6: Correlations and their significance in the architecture course, 2018, n=90

	Flipped online exercises	Assignment	Examination
Flipped online exercises	1	$r=0.26$	$r=0.31$
Assignment	* $p=0.0121$	1	$r=0.13$
Examination	* $p=0.0013$	$p=0.1884$	1

The correlations between the online exercises and all the other aspects are significant (see Table 6). The assignment and examination do not have a significant correlation.

4.3 Summary of the cases

The grading components based on student's activity correlate strongly with each other in all courses with the necessary data available. This strengthens the hypothesis that some students have a completion strategy of being active which is consistently observable throughout the course. With the exception of the architecture course in 2017, exercises have a significant correlation with assignments.

In the testing course, the assignment has a significant correlation with the examination as well. Surprisingly, this correlation vanishes totally in the architecture course. The only one notable difference between the courses was the group size: in the testing course, the assignment was made in pairs, whereas in the architecture course, the group size was 4–5. The missing correlation might be an indicator of a free-wheeler behaviour in the bigger groups, where a few students received a good grade without their own effort. There may be several reasons behind the uneven distribution of the effort, e.g., student(s) having the highest target grade have actually made the whole assignment considering this to be the easiest way for them to accomplish the task. The problem has already been addressed in the ongoing implementation of the course.

4.3.1 Benefit of pre-tasks is more apparent

The type of pre- and post-exercises varied remarkably including short essays, the definitions of terms and concepts, the applications of introduced methods, drawing UML diagrams and arguing on the pros and cons on the given topic. Some questions were provided with external pre-lecture materials, or students could exploit their own sources. If the course had both pre and post-exercises, the pre-exercises would be worth more activity points.

Answers were not limited with a minimum or maximum word count, although on the testing course short answers were warned to be of a partial value only. However, the expected answer length from course personnel side was around a couple of paragraphs to prove students' preparation for the upcoming topic.

While in the courses of this size it is to be anticipated that the quality of answers varies between students, most of the students had clearly put time and effort in their answers, writing often between 100 and 200 words, and even up to 400 words per question. The quality of the answers was mainly good, especially the longer answers discussing the topic comprehensively. Shorter answers were not necessarily low in quality, though more often so. While the answers were not graded as strictly as exam questions, the majority earned full points, some earned partial points and failed answers were rare. Based on the answers, it was evident that at least some of the students were using materials outside the provided lecture notes or linked external materials to familiarize themselves with the topic.

Based on the results between the software architecture course and the software testing course, the pre-questions seem to be more important for the students' learning or at least the lack of post-questions is not compromising the students' learning

outcome. The software testing course did not include post-questions at all, yet the correlation between the online exercises and the examination was stronger.

4.3.2 Neglected comment field

As described above, the students had the possibility to ask for a more detailed discussion about topics they found interesting when they answered the question related to the forthcoming lecture. It was anticipated that students would not use this possibility extensively, however, they almost neglected it. There were very few suggestions, even if the rare ones were taken into account seriously and handled in the lectures with piety. This open comment was used more to make questions like *'when will the assignment open?'*, or, *'why the feedback of the weekly online exercise has been delayed?'*.

To increase the participation and help students to reflect on their blind spots or topics of interests, constructive alignment, active instruction, and granting activity points for making relevant suggestions on comments could be profitable in the next course iterations.

5 DISCUSSION

In spite of the reduced teachers' work, the same level of the learning outcomes was achieved. In this respect, the flipped online exercises work fine. In addition, they seem to increase the connection between other graded components of the course. Although the results seem promising, the manifestation of the superiority of the flipped versions is too early. Definitely, they are not worse since the students obtained the same level with less teaching effort.

In the future, we are going to use and improve the idea of this study. Some evident things to improve the courses:

Practically a non-existent number of suggestions for lecture contents was a disappointment. However, this does not prove that the idea is not working. Instead, students should be encouraged to make suggestions. One way to do this is to offer activity points if the student proposes ideas in the comment field.

The weekly post-tasks have very small influence on learning and feedback of the students confirms this. We are likely to leave them out on both courses and concentrate on the weekly pre-tasks.

An additional discovery was that group assignments of more than two students do not work as intended. It has been known that in large groups some students are not active, but the correlations show that the phenomenon has a larger impact than expected. This can be addressed either by decreasing group sizes or by grading students individually. Enabling the individual grading is left for further study. The student feedback on this year's (2019) architecture course supports the idea of small groups.

Acknowledgments

Thanks to the Academy of Finland (grant N^o303694, i.e., *Skills, education and the future of work*) for their financial support.

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